

MODERN METHODS OF LEARNING ENGLISH: ANALYSIS OF THE MOST EFFECTIVE STRATEGIES TEACHING

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ANNOTATION

The relevance of English language proficiency has arisen over the past decade, as it expands the possibilities of distance learning and employment in foreign universities and companies. Just staying in a language environment does not give the proper level of English proficiency; therefore it is necessary to look for effective strategies to bring it to the C1- C2 level. In the course of this work, the best strategies described in research studies were examined, and then the strategies used by teachers in schools with the study of English as a second language were examined. The results are summarized and structured. The greatest emphasis was placed on strategies to promote fluency in speaking. The best results were shown by the strategies using a pair and group method of working with students. Also, the progress of students is accelerated by methods that help psychologically level the difference in language level within the class. Using the strategies described in this article, teachers can dramatically improve their students' English level and overcome the psychological blocks associated with learning. The work served as the foundation for further developing and applying our own methodology for learning English using virtual reality technologies.

Key words: English, teaching, methodology

INTRODUCTION

With the development of logistics and information technologies in the XXI century, the number and quality of communications between various countries have increased, including even those citizens who do not physically travel abroad. People introduce themselves, communicate and work through the Internet. The COVID-19 pandemic will complement the development of communications due to the need to organize distributed offices remotely.

In addition to the entertainment sphere, the need for international cooperation has significantly increased communication in an educational and working environment: a person from any region received the opportunity to study and work in foreign universities and companies without leaving his native country and his own quarter.

In this regard, knowledge of foreign languages and conversation skills is one of the most important facts of personal development and material well-being. English is coming to the fore as the main language of international communication.

The level of English language proficiency among the majority of graduates of Russian schools and universities does not allow you to take exams in foreign universities and communicate freely with potential employees. This gives rise to numerous discussions about the ways of improving the methodology of teaching English.

The well-known thesis about immersion in the English-speaking environment as an optimal method for a comprehensive understanding of new linguistic skills for a student is not always confirmed in practice. If you study the experience of an immigrant, who live and work in the USA for ten years, to discover that they will not be able to speak faster in the new language environment. This happens because of a psychological barrier, when a person is not sure that he will be able to fully understand the interlocutor and express his own thoughts.

A single teaching standard is not possible due to the difference between the groups being trained and the learning goals.

Therefore, you need to have several options and apply them depending on the needs of the specific group being trained.

This study was conducted in two stages: theoretical and practical.

At this academic event, I studied the research of scientists on pedagogy and teaching of the English language and identified the key advantages that we have at the moment.

The practical stage was conducted on the basis of a US school with English as a second language of instruction (ESL, English as a Second Language). These schools are attended by children of immigrants from various countries whose native language is not English. Accordingly, the main goal of the school is to achieve full integration of the student into the society of the USA, which requires fluency in English. I surveyed the students and teachers of the school to identify the most effective learning strategies. I have surveyed the students and teachers of the school, which will highlight the most effective teaching methods.

The study was conducted with fourth-grade teachers and students from a public school in Brooklyn, New York City. The school is equipped with modern technology such as tablet PCs and smart boards. The teaching staff consists of American and Russian specialists, with the Russian teachers serving as the main guides for the students in the new language environment and cultural atmosphere. The classroom microclimate was designed to facilitate maximum adaptation to the foreign country, mentality, traditions, and linguistic peculiarities. The students participated in the program as part of their regular school curriculum with an integrated ESL model. The group consisted of three boys and four girls, all of whom were originally from Russia and had arrived in the USA within the past 10 months, without any prior knowledge of English or American culture and traditions. The families of the participants live in a Russian-speaking environment and neighborhood, and communicate in Russian outside of school. Inside the school, they prefer to interact with Russian-speaking students and have had little exposure to English as a language of communication.

Despite not having a strong grasp of the English language, all the participants displayed impressive knowledge and skills in other fields that were taught in Russian. Moreover, the students exhibited the ability to think critically and analyze information logically. During their free time, they were most interested in engaging in physical activities and creative pursuits such as playing tennis, swimming, and playing musical instruments.

The classroom environment is centered around the principle of solidarity, where students are eager to assist one another both academically and through the various extracurricular activities. This makes it easier for those who are shy and may require additional support to feel more included and welcomed.

The main objective of this study is to compare various effective teaching methods and identify their key advantages in practice. The findings of this analysis can be used to develop a

new teaching methodology that incorporates the best practices of proven methods and utilizes modern IT industry tools not previously used in ESL and distance learning English schools.

According to day and this study precedes and is the right point for a more in-depth and specific study on the use of methodic of virtual reality and in teaching English.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Learning in bilingual education programs within ESL schools offers the opportunity to become fluent in two languages, including specialized vocabulary in diverse fields, which is a valuable asset in today's world. [1]

Another study has also expressed a similar point of view, emphasizing the importance of the connection between theoretical understanding and practical application of bilingualism in the process of mastering a second language. The research highlights the importance of fluency of speech, pronunciation skills, and interaction with the interlocutor. [2]

As someone who has attended ESL schools, I can attest to the fact that they offer a diverse range of learning strategies that have been proven effective. The main thing that sets these schools apart from traditional educational institutions, where English is typically taught as a foreign language, is that they place a special emphasis on developing conversational skills. It's widely recognized that being able to speak fluently and confidently is a crucial aspect of language learning, and ESL schools prioritize this goal accordingly [3].

When learning a foreign language, a student initially relies on mnemonic skills to memorize words, grammar rules, spelling, and other specifics. However, as the student begins to use the language in actual communication, other areas of the brain responsible for perception, thinking, and speech functions are activated. This leads to the formation of new neural connections, which helps the student acquire the language more effectively.

Students and immigrants often share a common fear of making mistakes and expressing themselves incorrectly, which can hinder their cognitive process. It's important for students to feel psychologically calm in order to learn effectively. When students are not afraid of making errors, they are more likely to engage with their teacher and the material, making it easier to learn and retain the information. [4]

Suk and Cole focused on the effectiveness of teaching parents techniques to facilitate speech: picture books, manuals and other visual materials.

This helped to establish the interaction of verbal and nonverbal communication, which gave a better effect compared to the isolated study of spoken or written sets of words. Elementary school students who comprehend the basics of communication, with the help of images, understood the story more fully, which removed the initial fear and became a positive trigger for further communication [5]. It has been noticed that students learn the language better when they are interested [6]. Also, the language should correspond to the level of development of the student [7].

The CALLA method was developed and expanded with the integration of language elements into educational content in other disciplines. The learning strategy included metacognitive, cognitive and socially effective directions [8]. In such methods, specific techniques are used, such as questions on the text, dictation of instructions, drawing up lists and presentation plans.

In general, many studies have proven that cooperation between an English teacher and teachers of other disciplines benefits the student. In order for cooperation to be effective, a

reasonable balance between subjects and the depth of integration of English into their study is important [9]. There should also be a clear correspondence of the language elements to the student's level of knowledge [10]. The gradual integration of programmatic language skills has proven itself well as students are ready, starting with classes that do not require cognitive cognition [11].

Communication between students plays a significant role. Excellent results were shown by the class, where the teachers were more like guides or companions in the classroom, orientated and focused on the students [12].

If the orientation of the listed approaches is summed up, then they can be grouped according to two main features:

1. Interaction with birthing fir trees. The connection between parents and the child in the process of mastering a foreign language is important for cultural immersion in the English-speaking environment, joint movement facilitates overcoming difficulties in the process of discussing them inside the family. Parallel training of a student and a parent allows you to form a powerful nonverbal image and motivation.

2. Other researchers focus on the student's communication with the class through integration various goals in the process of general education, including other disciplines. This allows you to form out-of-class tasks with visual elements and visual application of English in various fields, which expands the cognitive capabilities of students.

METHODOLOGY

Data collection was carried out by empirical and research methods. The primary data were collected from various publications and scientific papers in the field of pedagogy and teaching of the English language in printed publications and on Internet resources. In the course of further research I observed the work of the students, and then collected secondary data through the interview and questionnaires of students and teachers.

Classroom observations

During the study, educational observations were made on the work of students. Busy attended three times a week with the study of various aspects of lessons, such as student involvement, language literacy, fluency of the language. To track the dynamics of academic performance and was used the control diagram.

Student surveys

The students passed various surveys and tests, which concerned not only the educational process, but also behavioral patterns, abilities, and temperament. This information was especially useful for me, so I understood which technologies would work with children in the best way.

More than, after analyzing the psychological profile and the sweat of the students, it was easier to determine which religion motivates them the most. Another area of questionnaires and research is int heresy. An analysis of the interests is needed to understand which subjects are best chosen when developing a teaching program. Correlation diagrams of students' progress, expressed in numbers and percentages, were used to work with numerical data.

Surveys teaches fir

The surveys for teachers were conducted through individual interviews. During the interviews, I was keen on identifying the most effective strategies that would cater to the unique needs of students. I also sought to understand the factors that teachers consider in

choosing a particular strategy. Specifically, I was interested in the indicators that teachers use to determine which approach would be most effective. Additionally, I sought to learn how teachers measure success and whether they are open to implementing other promising strategies if the opportunity arises.

Research methods

I conducted my research using a constructive method that involved searching for additional solutions to improve English learning. I observed students and compared my findings with previous research papers. In addition, I utilized the search method to explore new discoveries in the field of conversational strategies, bilingual education, and TESOL. I paid close attention to the latest modern strategies and focused on the strategies of bilingual education that contribute to the development of oral speech and search for alternative solutions to the problem of language fluency and communication.

Furthermore, I used an empirical method that involved observing students and generalizing the results. The study was conducted in three stages, and it included observing students in individual tutoring lessons and in general lessons at school three times a week for two months.

Chronology of the study

The study took a total of 8 months to complete and was divided into five stages, each separated by a 3-week interval. These stages involved planning and studying, observing and conducting research, collecting data, analyzing the data, summarizing information, and engaging in critical reflection.

Data analysis

After the study, all the results were collected, grouped according to the answers, compared, compared and grouped according to the results. The results were analyzed by comparison with the data of scientific sources used in the course of the study, after which the conclusion was made and the main reports were compiled. The data collected using three research methods were interpreted in a constructive way with the derivation of additional solutions to the problem of language proficiency and communication. The search method helped to evaluate the results from the perspective of new discoveries in the field of conversational strategies, bilingual education and TESOL. The results of empirical data allowed us to correlate practical observations with the research base when compiling reports and concluding conclusions. All the data of the study were analyzed based on the responses of the participants. Completed questionnaires and interview transcripts were categorized for consistency and completeness of data. The most valuable data were based on observations made with the help of template interview. Direct observation was a fundamental way to study effective strategies used by teachers to stimulate the language development of students. Interviews were also used to determine the level of motivation of participants and their perception of the strategies used. The questions were open, the respondent gave answers in his own words. Interview questionnaires, in addition to the level of motivation, are ideal for data collection, since they contain individual records of each independent respondent based on their knowledge and experience. Personal interviews were also of great importance, as they provided more information about the opinions of students and teachers.

Results

Based on the collected data, I have identified the most effective strategies that contribute to the development of oral speech.

Teachers' responses

During the surveys, the main strategies of teachers for the development of students' language skills were established. The study revealed how it is possible to predict that this strategy will be effective. Additional measures that need to be taken to work with students with different levels of English proficiency have been identified.

During the analysis of the responses, the most effective strategies for improving conversational skills among ESL students and the mechanism of their practical application were identified. The criteria for the progress of students and an effective way of combining development strategies are also defined. Oral speech with listening, reading and writing strategies as part of the ESL course.

I give all the results below.

The elements of bilingual education that contribute to the development of oral speech

1. General terms of use

General articles of use include :

- Visual aids;
- joint training;
- generalization of knowledge;
- review and written digest of the contact, understood and language descriptions in the form of vocabulary, word forms, linguistic functions, practical tasks;
- communication within the framework of communication.

2. Specific articles

Specific items include :

- Talking points cards;
- forecasting using key illustrations;
- group task;
- lists of tags and rules;
- strategies forwarding problems;
- terminological card glasses with in ca cards;
- t paragraph of observations;
- introduction procedure;
- the method of finding the interlocutor;
- A journal of the use of diagrams for teaching understanding of causality and paraphrasing.

The most effective strategies aimed at individual perspiration and student.

Based on the analysis of the students' progress, the best individual strategies were determined:

- From the work of the oral retelling skills and conclusions from the rest;
- Analysis of cards with quotes on a specific topic with discussion in pairs in combination with watching a bright and inspiring video on the same topic, followed by a discussion of quotes between groups of students;

- observation map: the teacher hung pictures on the topic of the lesson in the four corners of the classroom, the students moved from picture to picture, recording their observations and conclusions;
- picture cards that were distributed to various groups; one group described the pictures, the other group guessed what they were describing;
- "solve the problem": groups wrote tasks on card glasses and exchanged them.

As can be predicted, what will be the effect of it?

It turned out that with regard to personal tasks, it is impossible to predict their effectiveness in advance. But we can definitely say that strategies involving teamwork and pair work better and are more effective, because in the process a relaxed and comfortable atmosphere is formed for students, removing fears that block learning.

Additional measures to be taken with students with different levels of language proficiency.

It was found that for optimal performance, before starting training, students must pass a test to determine the level of language proficiency in order to receive feasible tasks. At the same time, students with a low level of language proficiency can be placed in the same group with students with a higher level. I found out that students are willing to cooperate, helping each other. In order for weaker students not to develop self-doubt, additional work and help are needed from the teacher's side, allowing to catch up with stronger students.

Other articles and ideas

It was stated that each teacher had his own effective approach, but I first of all analyzed the following components:

- Students' motivation
- Atmosphere in the lesson
- Practical application of language skills

It turned out that the teacher plays a significant role in the willingness of students to speak English and discuss various problems with other peers. According to all teachers, a comfortable atmosphere is necessary for this. This helps to relieve stress and use the language unconsciously, without fear of making mistakes, concentrating mainly on what the child wants to say, and not on realizing the fact that he speaks a foreign language.

Practical application implies that any topic chosen for the lesson should it leads to real life situations, where students were emotionally motivated and they themselves wanted to use a foreign language where Russian is usually used.

The ability to teach and motivate students plays a very important role in the development of English literacy .The complex and interconnected nature of languages has a long history of development, which, when presented intensely, can imitate the associative memory of students in contrast to mechanical memorization.

The relaxed atmosphere, in addition to the removed stress, expands the possibilities of cognitive interaction and development of linguistic abilities in the process of live communication.

Discussions of various topics with the possibility to express their own opinion stimulate analytical thinking and provide information about problematic language skills for the student. Each of the interviewees teaches and emphasized that any strategy should be applied in certain conditions, conditions and situations. These strategies should be thought out in

advance: the teacher should understand why he should apply this strategy and what it will lead to. I also found out the most important obstacle in the motivation: some students do not fully understand the meaning of the language and study it to exclude it for higher grades in exams. The ICU will explain to them how knowledge of English will make their lives easier, the results will improve quickly.

Analysis of student responses

The most effective strategies for improving conversational skills.

I noticed that the student, the cat does not grab his confidence and prefers to listen in silence while others are talking. What will encourage those students, teach, and help them generate minimal from vet s during pair and group exercises. Such answers can be especially useful for beginners. The received stock from the vet does not prevent you from focusing on the statements of other students.

Another effective strategy for improving conversational skills was script recognition. Some situations in communication are associated with a predictable course of dialogue, a scenario. In such situations, you can see the relationship between the replicas of the participants in the dialogue. In this way, teachers help students to anticipate the answer. During such interactive classes, children receive many options for developing practical language skills.

Points of application of potentially effective strategies for children with initially different knowledge and skills

When students have a clear understanding of the learning goal, their motivation to learn increases. This measure allows them to understand the task and its significance. To further strengthen the goal, specific values and benefits that come with learning English can be highlighted. When students understand the relevance of language proficiency in their professional lives, they are more likely to put in the effort to achieve it. Teachers can increase students' motivation by linking lesson content to their intended profession.

Another effective strategy, especially for students with different levels of knowledge and skills, is to focus on real-world knowledge and skill application. Even if the lesson is theoretical, teachers can increase its relevance by explaining the practical significance of the knowledge being taught.

A teacher's enthusiasm and positive emotions can also inspire students. When teachers show their own enthusiasm and reveal interesting and non-trivial aspects of the subjects being taught, even initially disinterested students may become curious and more engaged in the material.

Criteria student's success in fluent speech

Based on the results, various factors were established that indicate the success of students in fluent speech.

The main evaluation criterion is how much the student pays attention to the little things. The more proficient he is in the language, the less mental effort he spends trying to understand the interlocutor's thought. The perception of oral speech expands from the essence to the smallest details.

Performing exercises based on the technique of paying attention to small things improves fluency of speech. In addition, the teacher can modify other techniques and supplement them with exercises for attention to detail. This accelerates the progress of students.

The technique of paying attention to the little things in combination with the presentation of facts allows the class to develop towards expanding the range of topics. Along the way, the ability to correctly pose questions and answer them develops, which allows you to more fully assimilate the linguistic structure of the English language.

Testing attention to detail is often considered as the main criterion for a student's mastery of fluent speech.

This is an effective way of combining the development of oral speech with others strategic listening, reading and writing.

Interactive storytelling showed the best results of the combined strategy. This is an effective way to learn English while combining listening, repetition and constant practice. The student hears real words in English and, repeating them to himself, after a while begins to speak fluently.

The students practiced speaking by listening to simple words, reviews and stories. Such a set of activities within the framework of the lesson is an excellent option for students who have a basic level of understanding and the ability to understand meaning-forming words.

Short stories work well with other listening, reading and writing strategies in the ESL course, as they promote slow but conscious reading. Even students with advanced English proficiency benefit by consolidating their knowledge of the language and making their spoken English more natural.

Conclusions

Based on the results of the study and analysis, the following conclusions can be drawn:

1. The results of the research are important for professional language practice, because they reveal the practical application of the effects of the methods used by teachers. Using the methods proposed in this article, teachers will be able to take students to a new level of English proficiency. In addition to improving skills, the listed strategies facilitate the learning process, make it more interesting and motivate students.

2. The results of the research will help in the development of future research, which will cover the entire basic spectrum of the applied techniques and correlate with similar approaches in training and education.

3. I have done a lot of scientific work, summarized and structured the data of key studies over the past 40 years. In addition to teaching English, I studied the works of scientists from related fields.

4. It was possible to find the most effective methods that contribute to the maximum development of oral speech and fluency of speech.

5. The individual presence in the lessons allowed us to develop skills and think over a combination of different skills, extracting maximum benefit from them.

6. I have identified the key areas by which the effect of the event can be assessed: motivation, atmosphere and practice. I have also structured and grouped the works of teachers that strengthen compliance with students in these key areas.

7. The moments became clear, on which the applicability of the article depends: the conditions, the conditions of the, situation, as well as the thought-out of the procedure before its application.

8. I have established which strategies are more effective: pair and group classes with interactive techniques, such as games with quotes, observation cards and picture cards.

9. The choice of a course of study should directly depend on the age and development of the student, academic performance, level of motivation and communication with other peers.

10. Each article should be carefully selected, studied, thought out and applied with the prediction of results, deadlines, setting goals, in combination with other strategies. This is what makes it ideal and effective during teaching and learning.

11. I studied and showed the mechanism of application of various methods for children with initially different knowledge and skills, explored ways to improve the motivation of students with initially low level of language proficiency.

12. This study was the right point for the development of my own methodology of teaching English using virtual reality technologies.

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